

Analysis of Research Results on the Influence of Ultraviolet Rays on the Human Body and Various Microorganisms

Tosheva D. R., Abdullaev R. K.

Bukhara State Medical Institute Urgench branch of the Tashkent Medical Academy

Abstract: *The importance of natural ultraviolet rays for the human body has been proven in many studies, but although their positive effects on pathological conditions occurring in the body are shown from a clinical point of view, data on the study of their action Immuno-microbiological aspects are few, and the results of these studies are scattered, interpreted, analyzed and presented in the form of a review of scientific sources.*

Key words: *ultraviolet rays, wavelength, infrared rays, x-rays, electromagnetic waves.*

The shorter the wavelength of visible light, the deeper it penetrates the skin and vice versa. Infrared light has the property of generating heat, so it is also called thermal energy. As a result of thermal exposure, skin receptors reflexively cause the expansion and redness of blood vessels. For this reason, infrared rays are used to reduce pain.

Materials and methods: Ultraviolet (UV) radiation is invisible electromagnetic radiation occupying the spectral range between visible and X-rays. UV wavelengths from 400 to 180 nm are part of the light spectrum. Depending on the wavelength, the UV spectrum is divided into 3 areas: long-wave UV radiation (LWUV) - 400-320 nm; medium-wave UV radiation (MWUV) - 320-280 nm; short-wave UV radiation (QTUB) - 280-180 nm. It is known that in natural conditions the source of UV rays is the sun, but only its long-wave part reaches the earth's surface. Very short-wave radiation is absorbed by the atmosphere at an altitude of 30-50 km above the earth's surface.

An increase in hematopoietic elements and an increase in oxidative processes in the affected area lead to an improvement in metabolism and a faster absorption of pathological products. Surgical technique and general principles of patient care are important for reducing the incidence of wound infection. It is rare that one factor takes the leading place; only the sum of several factors leads to the desired result. When the body is exposed to infrared and ultraviolet rays (UV rays), symptoms of redness appear on the skin. Infrared and UV rays come from natural and artificial light sources; the sun is a natural source of light, and various devices are artificial light sources. UV rays are obtained using mercury-quartz tube lamps.

UTUB and O'TUB interact primarily with the proteins of the cell protoplasm, and QTUB - with the nucleoproteins of the cell nucleus. At the same time, QTUB blood irradiation has a predominantly immunostimulating effect, and UTUB irradiation improves the rheological properties of the blood and microcirculation.

It is known that UV radiation was first discovered by the German physicist Johann Wilhelm Ritter. On the electromagnetic wave scale, UV rays are between visible light and X-rays from 10 to 380 nm. In 1803, the Russian physicist V.V. Petrov first described artificial light obtained using an electric arc, and in 1859, the French neurologist J.M. Zharko suggested that the skin's reaction to electric arc radiation is similar to the effect of sunlight. In 1890-1892, the Russian doctor P.V. Ewald used irradiation of workers suffering from rheumatism and neuralgic pain. E. Nott first used autovenous ultraviolet blood irradiation

(AVUBN) in Germany in 1928 to treat septic patients. He and W. Hancock infected dogs with hemolytic streptococci until they developed sepsis, then irradiated their blood with UV rays and pumped it through UV-transmitting quartz glass attached to blood vessels. H. Havlicek achieved a positive clinical effect in 1934 by injecting patients with UV-irradiated blood. In 1975, F. A. Popp described the nature of UV photon energy in living cells. He proved that energy in a cell can be transmitted with biological information to another organism through space using UV photons.

Currently, high- and low-pressure fluorescent sources are used to generate UV rays, which allows for the production of integral UV radiation. The biological effect of UV rays is considered to be the photoelectric effect - the ability of molecules of substances that make up the cells of living organisms to absorb radiation quanta and, as a result, participate in various photochemical reactions that change their structure and functions. This process leads to a change in the structure of DNA, RNA and protein molecules that are most sensitive to radiation, the rupture of weak bonds in protein molecules, the disintegration of complex molecules into simple ones, the formation of free radicals, the occurrence of cellular mutations, and the release of biologically active substances (histamine, acetylcholine, prostaglandin).

As a result of desorption of proteins and carbohydrates from the pre-membrane layer of blood cells under the influence of UV radiation, the possibility of interaction of various blood elements with receptor proteins at the intercellular distance increases. UV irradiation causes dilation of the microcirculatory bed vessels, normalizes the blood coagulation system, activates metabolic processes in tissues. With UV irradiation of blood, the saturation of formed elements of the blood with oxygen is stimulated and its ionic permeability increases, which leads to an increase in the amount of oxyhemoglobin and an increase in the oxygen capacity of the blood. As a result of activation of lipid peroxidation processes and the destruction of thiol compounds and alpha-tocopherol in the membranes of erythrocytes and leukocytes, free radicals and hydroperoxides appear, capable of neutralizing toxic products in the blood.

This is B- radiation physiological effect neuroreflexive , neuro -humoral . and biochemical of the processes consists of This is from radiation intensity, duration, area, localization, skin UV- rays sensitivity and body is determined by the initial functional states. Its own economic efficiency, simplicity, safety, in the body surface coming biological effects diversity, side effects absence of effects and high therapeutic efficiency due to the last ten in the annuals photohemotherapy dynamically developing.

Grimes D.R. et al. According to their data, UV irradiation is divided into 2 groups by its effect on biological objects: photochemical and destructive action, in addition, biogenic and abiogenic action of UV irradiation are distinguished. Irradiation of each zone has a number of biological effects, but according to the most important effect, zone A is pigment-forming, zone V is anti-rachitic, zone C is bactericidal. Zone A of UV radiation has a hygienic, invigorating effect.

It has been shown that the abiogenic effect of UV radiation occurs with an increase in the total radiation dose. In such cases, DNA synthesis processes and functional activity of the central nervous system are suppressed, hypertrophy of the cells of the fascicular and reticular zones of the adrenal cortex develops, as well as disturbances in vitamin metabolism, and oncogenesis increases. The negative consequences of UV radiation for humans include bactericidal action, carcinogenic action, phototoxicosis, photoallergy in the presence of single or photosensitizers.

infection, indicated an increase in immunobiological potential. In these cases, UV radiation cannot have a direct bactericidal effect due to the small absorption depth (0.2-1.0 mm).

When absorbing rays, complex biophysical processes occur in the microbial cell in the form of denaturation and coagulation of protein molecules, nucleic acids due to their effect on DNA and RNA.

The result of these changes is the appearance of lethal mutations leading to the destruction of microorganisms, inactivation of the genome. It should be noted that the death of microorganisms occurs only under the influence of large erythematous doses of UV rays, while small doses enhance their reproduction or change biological properties. It has been established that QTUB radiation has a bactericidal effect on *Staphylococcus spp*, *Streptococcus spp*, *Salmonella spp*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli* and the influenza virus.

Bernard J.J. et al., according to data, the d- sensitizing effect is achieved by repeated UV irradiation, which leads to a decrease in the amount of histamine, a significant increase in the histamine-peptic index (an indicator of the body's ability to inactivate histamine). This effect is associated with increased activity of protective antihistamine mechanisms. The analgesic effect is associated with changes in the nerve receptor-effector structures of the skin, which contribute to a change in skin sensitivity under the influence of erythematous doses of UV radiation. Histidine and histidine decarboxylase, detected in skin dialysates in the experiment, indicated a decrease in excitability, inhibition of the activity of various organs, and inhibition of nerve endings. Similar opinions were expressed by Markevich P.S.

non-specific resistance and correction of cellular and humoral immunity under the influence of QTUB irradiation of blood is based on interferon, lysozyme production, activation of the complement system, increased phagocytic activity of leukocytes, an increase in the titer of immunoglobulins and a number of other indicators [1,4].

UV radiation is a chemically and biologically active factor. This activity is widespread in biology, medicine and agriculture. It has been established that under the influence of high-energy UV radiation, photoelectric and photochemical processes occur in the tissues of the body, which, in turn, lead to a number of biochemical changes that have a significant impact on metabolism [1, 3].

These are B- rays under the influence of photochemical vitamin D on the skin, by the way the harvest will be Prevention of vitamin D deficiency or care for Specially in combination with UV radiation preparation of a pen of a hand , the results of the conducted studies were also published, its rickets prevention receive for the case of use is described . Observations that's all show that vitamin D k elib due to hunting for the harvest is released phosphorus-calcium development of rickets associated with metabolic disorders prevention will receive UV radiation minimum requirement it is necessary to make the amount per day safe amounted to 10% of the dose.

Neil, who studied the effects of UV rays on the human body. R.E. There is al . according to the data, k is internal in doses UV radiation brain processes cortex activates, mental performance , muscle tone, physical. durable to and rest efficiency increases , addition napkin harvest be processes activate it process slow healing of wounds and wounds on treatment is used. Also ontogenesis in the human body in the process of UV radiation excess from the effect of protection to do effective methods formed league is presented - them skin thickening, this is pigmentation They say that this is dirty work, and this is B- radiation. pigment h ocyl acter effect of melanin this leads to the formation of .

It is established that 151-6040 J/ m² GI U B- ray dose under the influence of *Clostridium histolyticum* free of collagenase molecules catalytic activity immobilized in chitosan from the matrix to the situation than more modulation and ngan . 3020 J/ m² enzymatic rhythm in a dose of UV radiation after, its activity decreased by 9% kuzatil gan , in acid who laughs middle molecular and high molecular chitosan in matrix collagenase immobilization given enzyme activity in any dose change not identified. In China adsorb TS yes bacterial collagenase a free compared to form to UV radiation relatively g heterogeneous biocatalysts stability increasing to i come, bro Enzyme and middle and high molecular chitosan matrix between bonds formation immobilized U B- radiation of the drug durability significant effect Show me , is it possible to adsorb TC yes during collagenase a What about three? The structure of hardness increase occurred due to [1,2].

Results and discussion : According to the results of the study, the fun period from non-healing wounds received microorganisms sound other wave is suppressed by UV rays in the ranges. Bloody if the son of the colony in physiotherapy of wounds acceptance made in modes with polarized rays , node lu kli red and infrared, continuous middle and CT UB irradiated with ganom, such an effect to do unison to the basement come on take it, bro full date ts i only by effect The quantitative approved indicator of the HCKB is achieved by UV irradiation . As it turned out, the role of the microbial factor in the development of the infectious process because for the most part in cases where he was injured care dynamics specification and feature determines and for this pathology effective allows to choose treatment [6].

Rasulov M. M. in the opinion of microorganisms resistance to antibiotics partly their to the effects of UV rays durability suitable will come To study the results of UV radiation, especially short wave sanatorium in the testing ground showed the effect.

Filimonova O. Ya. control material both from UV radiation before and after from crumbs on the surface of the gum of the structure used 1 hour After curing the prosthesis with UV rays, the sterilization effect was observed in 60% of cases , in 40% of cases. microflora in the prosthesis is preserved the rest (*Candida species*, *Neisseria species* - from 10^4 thousand HQB / ml). The obtained results UV radiation antibacterial effect prove this

Mouth diseases of the oral cavity purulent microflora of the wound exudes with complications in 37% of cases in the study *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli* in 12% of the stick existence determine Ngan. This study *in test tube* oral cavity microorganisms UV wave range length laser sensitivity to radiation I show me Nurlan Adi Gan 3 cm from the surface and with UV irradiation duration of 5 minutes bacteriostatic, at a distance of 1 cm a bactericidal effect was observed.

Lepilin A. V- spectrum UB laser on the territory and LED radiation reference (*S.aureus* ATSS 25923, *Escherichia coli* ATSS 25922, *Enterococcus faecalis* ATSS 29912) and inside the hospital strains effect experimental study do it bro In the experiment microorganisms 10^4 concentration of cells / ml at the input of the suspension used Laser beam is stable and labile methods used , stable method from the center of the Petri dish with irradiation of seeds upwards It is fixed, labile and gradually covers the entire surface. 5 minutes in diameter during moved. E k mal and Petri dishes 1 8 -24 hours during 37°C Incubate in a thermostat at room temperature . Radiation to the dose depends on the effect to determine and indirectly selected adequacy of exposure (5 min). Justification for the labile method was used. The effectiveness of laser and LED radiation on reference and nosocomial strains is shown.

Zhdanova O. S. The ability of *P.aeruginosa* to synthesize pyocyanin under stress caused by UV radiation was studied. It was found that the photophysical properties of pyocyanin allow us to consider it as a compound capable of photoactivation by both violet and UV radiation; individual cell colonies that survived irradiation lost the ability to synthesize pigment, which was assumed to be associated with the ability of the pyocyanin precursor (shikimic acid) to remove free radicals. The authors showed that the loss of *P.aeruginosa* pigment under stress (UV irradiation) is a protective adaptation mechanism. It was proven that under extreme conditions, pigment synthesis ceases and resumes when transferred to normal conditions, which ensures the survival of the microbial culture under such conditions.

To date, it has been established that the maximum bactericidal effect is provided by short-wave UV irradiation with a wavelength of 200 to 300 nm, causing inactivation of various microorganisms - bacteria, viruses, fungi. It has been proven that the effect of UV radiation depends on the energy of exposure or dose (J / cm^2), determined by the product of the radiation intensity (W / cm^2) and the duration of irradiation . The bactericidal effect of UV radiation is based on photochemical reactions that cause irreversible damage to DNA. In addition to DNA, UV affects other cellular structures, especially RNA and the cell membrane. The most effective inactivating effect is provided by QTUB radiation with a

wavelength of 200-295 nm. It has been shown that radiation in this range is well absorbed by purine and pyrimidine nitrogenous bases of DNA, which are the main targets of the lethal and mutagenic effect of UV radiation on biosystems.

Grechnikova V. Yu. The aim of the conducted research was to theoretically and practically substantiate the effect of UV radiation of a xenon lamp on *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella typhimurium*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Hafnia alvei*. Based on the results of the work, the bactericidal efficiency of one of the irradiation options was determined, which determines that the studied method of physical disinfection is a leader in terms of high efficiency and safety and a very promising method for use in livestock buildings. disinfection. The results obtained determined the need to determine the bactericidal effect of pulsed xenon UV irradiation on other types of microorganisms.

J/m^2 ^{UV} radiation (240-390 nm) The effect of doses on lymphocyte membrane markers was studied. It was shown that the composition of their subpopulations changes during incubation of UV-irradiated lymphocytes. An increased expression level of CD3⁺, CD19⁺, CD8⁺, CD16⁺, CD25⁺ and CD95⁺ cells was detected. At the same time, lymphocytes were activated in the form of an increase in the number of CD25⁺ and CD95⁺ cells, and the number of apoptotic cells increased in a dose-dependent manner.

Also surface molecules of human T-lymphocytes (markers CD2⁺, CD11a⁺, CD3⁺, CD4⁺, CD8⁺) 151-1359 J/m^2 . The effect of UV radiation (240-390 nm) was studied. It was found that 151-906 J/m^2 UV irradiation in the indicated dose range contributed to an increase in the expression level of CD3⁺, CD4⁺, CD8⁺ markers. The expression level of intercellular adhesion molecules CD2⁺ and Cd11a⁺ by T lymphocytes was 151-906 J/m^2 . It has been shown that doses remain at this level for intact cells after exposure to UV radiation. UV radiation 1359 J/m^2 . The dose induces a decrease in the expression level of CD2⁺, Cd11a⁺ and CD3⁺ markers, and it has also been shown to cause an increase in co-receptor CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ molecules by T-lymphocytes.

Radzhabov A.A. According to the data, the essence of photodynamic therapy (PDT) is that many biological objects (cancer cells, microorganisms) accumulate photosensitizing dyes, as a result of which they become sensitive to the effects of low-intensity laser radiation of the corresponding wavelength. The author proved that PDT of purulent wounds of soft tissues using photoditazine and amphiphilic polymers leads to a clear activation of the processes of wound cleansing from necrotic tissue, fibrin masses and colonies of microorganisms in the area of the primary wound channel. He came to the conclusion that this method of treatment is effective and superior to traditional methods according to clinical, histological and bacteriological studies.

It was found that in UV-irradiated lymphocytes, the increase in the activity of the mitochondrial enzyme glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase is associated with the activation of their synthesis *de novo*. In addition, the synthesis of superoxide dismutase and some interleukins (IL-1b and IL-2) increased. Incubation of photomodified cells in a medium without blood plasma led to the uncoupling of respiration and phosphorylation, and a decrease in the amount of ATP in lymphocytes.

Simonova N.V. The aim of the study was to evaluate the comparative effectiveness of reamberin and cytoflavin in correcting free radical lipid oxidation processes induced by UV irradiation in rat body membranes. The use of succinic antioxidants under UV irradiation resulted in stabilization of peroxidation processes against the background of increased physical endurance in rats. Intraperitoneal administration of cytoflavin at a dose of 100 mg/kg succinate to laboratory animals prevented the accumulation of lipid peroxidation products and increased the activity of the main components of the antioxidant system in rat blood plasma, which was superior to the effect of succinate at a dose of reamberin of 100 mg/kg under UV irradiation.

To increase the activity level of mice and rats irradiated with UV rays, a mixture of nettle, birch and maple leaves in a ratio of 1:1:1, 8 g of tincture dissolved in 200 g of boiling water was administered orally. 20 minutes before exposure to UV rays. Tindirma was prescribed daily at a dose of 5 ml / kg for 28 days. The method allowed to expand the arsenal of drugs with actoprotective activity and increase the effectiveness of UV rays on mice and rats without the use of relatively expensive pharmacological drugs with side effects.

Summary: UV radiation ranges from 25 to 100 mJ/cm². had a reducing effect on MS-2 and RV phages determined by traditional methods at doses up to At UBN doses of 80 and 100 mJ/cm², complete inactivation of MS-2 and PV phages in water was reported. At the same time, the same doses of UV irradiation had a slight reducing effect on PV, HAV RNA, isolated free PV and HAV RNA/C, which were stable and detected by RT-PCR in water at all UV doses, including The administration of doses of 80 and 100 mJ/cm² continued.

Thus, clinical and experimental studies have been conducted to study the distribution of UV rays in nature, the effect on the human body, cells of its immune system and microorganisms belonging to different genera and species, as well as their positive impact on the human body under various conditions. doses, as well as their bactericidal and bacteriostatic effect on reference and nosocomial strains of microorganisms. However, these studies have not been comprehensively studied, so the study of the immunobiological aspects of the effects of UV rays has not lost its relevance and necessity.

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